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Satisfaction with Leisure in the Italian Regions During the Period 2005-2022

It grew on average by 1.72% between 2005 and 2022 in the Italian regions

Istat calculates the value of satisfaction with free time. The variable represents the percentage of people aged 14 and over who declare themselves very or quite satisfied with their free time out of the total number of people aged 14 and over. The data takes into consideration the 20 Italian regions in the period between 2005 and 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of satisfaction with leisure in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for value of satisfaction with leisure in 2022 with a value of 76 units, followed by Umbria with a value of 71.2 and from Liguria with an amount equal to 69 units. In the middle of the table are Lazio with an amount of 66.6, followed by Valle d'Aosta and Calabria with a value of 65.8. Puglia closes the ranking with a value of 61.2 units, followed by Sardinia with a value of 60.5 units and Sicily with an amount of 58.2 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in satisfaction with free time between 2005 and 2022. Calabria is in first place in terms of value of the percentage change in satisfaction with free time between 2005 and 2022 with a value equal to 14.24% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 57.6 units up to a value of 65.8 units or equal to an amount of 8.2 units. Puglia follows with a variation equal to an amount of 13.33 units corresponding to a variation from an amount of 54 units up to a value of 61.2 units or equal to a variation of 7.2 units. In third place is Campania with a variation equal to an amount of 8.49% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 60.1 units up to a value of 65.2 units or equal to a variation of 5.1 units. In the middle of the table we find the Marche region with a growth in satisfaction with leisure equal to +2.24% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 62.5 units up to a value of 63.9 units or equal to an amount of 1.4 units. Molise follows with a variation equal to +1.37% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 65.8 units up to a value of 66.7 units or equal to an amount of 0.9 units. In eleventh place is Lombardy with a variation equal to an amount of 1.18% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 68 units up to a value of 68.8 units or equal to an amount of 0.8 units. Abruzzo closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of -3.08% corresponding to a variation from 64.9 units up to a value of 62.9 units corresponding to a variation of -2.00 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia follows with a variation equal to an amount of -3.7% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 67.5 units up to a value of 65 units. And finally Valle d'Aosta with a variation equal to an amount of -6.53% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 70.4 units up to a value of 65.8 units. On average, the value of satisfaction with free time grew by 1.72%, equal to a variation from an amount of 64.7 units up to a value of 65.8 units.

Satisfaction with free time in Italian macro-regions. Satisfaction with free time increased in all Italian macro-regions with the exception of the Islands where there was a decrease of -0.68%. In the other

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Italian macro-regions, the value of satisfaction with free time grew in percentage terms, recording an amount of +8.69% in Southern Italy, +5.6% in Southern Italy, +1.98% in Central Italy, +1.83% in the North-East, +1.8% in the North, +1.63% in the North-West. However, a significant gap persists between the southern macro-region and the central-northern regions. In fact, the value of satisfaction with free time in the South is 6.89% lower than the corresponding value in the Centre, -6.61% compared to the North-East, -8.12% compared to the North, -9.06 % compared to the North-West. The result is therefore a significant gap between Southern Italy and Central-Northern Italy in terms of satisfaction with free time.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Campania, Puglia, Sicily, Sardinia, Basilicata, Calabria;
- Cluster 2: Lombardy, Tuscany, Liguria, Emilia Romagna, Valle d'Aosta, Umbria, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Marche, Piedmont, Molise, Trentino Alto Adige, Veneto, Lazio, Abruzzo.

From the point of view of the average of the clusters we can note that the average value of cluster 2 tends to be higher than the average value of cluster 1, i.e. the following relationship occurs: $C2 > C1$. We can see that cluster 1 is made up of a set of regions that have low values of satisfaction with leisure. These are regions that essentially coincide with Southern Italy with the exception of Molise and Abruzzo which instead have a high level of satisfaction with leisure time. It is therefore confirmed that Italy is divided in two also in access to entertainment services with a southern population that appears to be less satisfied than the central-northern population.

Conclusions. From the analysis conducted we can summarize the following propositions:

- Satisfaction with free time grew in the Italian regions by 1.72% between 2005 and 2022;
- The value of satisfaction with free time has grown especially in the southern regions, particularly in Campania, Puglia and Calabria;
- The southern regions have a much lower value of satisfaction with leisure time than the central-northern regions.

The result is therefore the picture of a particular form of inequality detected at a geographical level, namely that relating to satisfaction with free time. However, it is clear that in this sector, a very relevant role must be given to income. In fact, consumers can afford to purchase goods and services to consume in their free time only after having satisfied lower-level human needs. Since income in southern regions is often set at a subsistence level, it follows that many southerners do not have the resources to buy goods that they can consume in their free time. The lack of demand also results in a reduced supply of services and goods to be consumed in free time. Often the offer of entertainment services is created with public resources through the programming of local and regional authorities. However, this public investment in sustaining an offer of entertainment goods and services cannot alone generate a relative demand in the absence of adequate incomes.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Soddisfazione per il tempo libero					
Rank	Regione	2005	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Calabria	57,6	65,8	8,2	14,24
2	Puglia	54	61,2	7,2	13,33
3	Campania	60,1	65,2	5,1	8,49
4	Piemonte	64,4	67,4	3	4,66
5	Umbria	68,8	71,2	2,4	3,49
6	Lazio	64,4	66,6	2,2	3,42
7	Veneto	62,4	64,3	1,9	3,04
8	Emilia-Romagna	65,8	67,4	1,6	2,43
9	Marche	62,5	63,9	1,4	2,24
10	Molise	65,8	66,7	0,9	1,37
11	Lombardia	68	68,8	0,8	1,18
12	Trentino-Alto Adige	75,4	76	0,6	0,8
13	Sicilia	58,5	58,2	-0,3	-0,51
14	Toscana	67,6	67,2	-0,4	-0,59
15	Basilicata	63,8	63,2	-0,6	-0,94
16	Sardegna	61,2	60,5	-0,7	-1,14
17	Liguria	70,9	69	-1,9	-2,68
18	Abruzzo	64,9	62,9	-2	-3,08
19	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	67,5	65	-2,5	-3,7
20	Valle d'Aosta	70,4	65,8	-4,6	-6,53

Soddisfazione per il tempo libero				
Macro-regione	2005	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Sud	58,7	63,8	5,1	8,69
Mezzogiorno	58,9	62,2	3,3	5,6
Centro	65,5	66,8	1,3	1,98
Nord-est	65,4	66,6	1,2	1,83
Nord	66,5	67,7	1,2	1,8
Nord-ovest	67,3	68,4	1,1	1,63
Isole	59,2	58,8	-0,4	-0,68

